

D1.4: Consolidated Action Plans

Author:
Rob Davies (MDR)

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Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction and methodology.....	4
2. Content and metadata.....	5
3. Additional content providers.....	11
4. Politics of aggregation.....	16
5. Intermediate Metadata Schema.....	20
6. Infrastructure testing.....	23
7. Microservice (SaaS) testing.....	27
8. Online training.....	30
9. Conclusions.....	33
Annex I – Template for country action plans.....	34
Annex 2 - Action plan and timetable	36
Content partner objectives: overview.....	36
Content partner objectives.....	38
Microservices: timetable for testing.....	56
Infrastructure : timetable for testing.....	56

1. Introduction and methodology

This Deliverable is a result of *Task 1.3 Action Planning* in the LoCloud workplan. The main steps carried out corresponded to the following activities in the Description of Work:

Task 1.3.2 The LoCloud partner in each territory will convene, or otherwise associate with, a planning group involving key players in the cultural sector by Month 4.

Task 1.3.3 Action plans will be prepared by the country partners to identify the steps needed in a territory to implement the IaaS or SaaS solutions for aggregation by Month 7.

Following the kick off meeting the partner in each country was asked to complete an initial draft plan by M4, in order to stimulate thinking about how the work of LoCloud is to be accomplished in each territory, what their role will be in testing tools and services and to assess the challenges to be faced. Following review and discussions at the three content provider workshops held in M5 and 6, partners were then asked to complete a revised plan using the template at Annex 1. This document is a consolidated summary of those reports.

Responses related to dissemination plans and specifically promotion of the LoCloud Competition have been made available to the partners responsible for dissemination planning in WP5 but are and are not incorporated in this report.

This Deliverable may usefully be read in conjunction with the following:

D1.3 Content and metadata analysis

D1.5 Requirements analysis

The LoCloud content partners' content action plans were reviewed during April-May 2014 to establish a consolidated action plan detailing the timing and objectives for each partner which is provided as Annex 2. The text of the deliverable was updated to include additional details gathered from partners during the review process; detailed action plans for specific collections from the Discovery Programme and RCE provided as Annex 2 in the version 1 of this deliverable has been integrated into the document.

2. Content and metadata

The content partners were asked when they foresee the metadata for the content that they plan to make available to Europeana being ready for ingestion. Partners in 15 countries indicated that they expected metadata to be ready before the end 2014:

Austria, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Turkey, United Kingdom.

Fig 1 Countries planning to have metadata ready for ingestion in 2014

The detailed timetable is provided in Annex 2.

Country content provider	Comments
Austria (AIT)	We will enrich the data, provide unique identifiers and publish the content in the Europeana Local Austria national portal (OAI provider) from where it can be harvested by Europeana. We have already experience in setting up an OAI provider in EDM and therefore we plan to set up an OAI provider in EDM format for our Austrian LoCloud content providers.
Belgium (Provincie Limburg)	The following actions need to be done: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capture metadata Enrich metadata Provide unique identifiers/URIs Map metadata to an intermediary schema Quality assure metadata is ready for Europeana
Bulgaria (PSRL)	PSRL has a good experience ingesting data in Europeana since it operates as one of the Bulgarian aggregators. There is a repository set up by PSRL supporting OAI-PMH.

Country content provider	Comments
Croatia (GKR)	<p>GKR needs to approach different local organizations, some with digitized collections and some with interesting collections to be digitized. We would probably have to take part in preparing suitable metadata from these organizations.</p> <p>GKR needs to upgrade our digital library (SVeVID) to new OMEKA 2 version, upload and prepare new content and metadata. It will need to complete all of the steps listed.</p>
Cyprus (CUT)	<p>We are now working on the following: 1. To inform the majority of the CH stakeholders about the importance to digitize their content and create their Metadata. In addition to have the minimum infrastructure available for the online availability of their collection. 2. We are now working closely with the Archive of the Limassol Municipality (the city of our university) – For this collection we are working on publishing content online and metadata enrichment. We will need to map metadata to an intermediary LoCloud schema. This content will be ready to ingestion by the end of the second semester 2014. However, we would like to test the results of our work by using the LoCloud infrastructure, the soonest possible.</p> <p>[We need to do] all of the steps listed. Please have in mind that some of the CY CH stakeholders are not aware about the issues mentioned above (as we understand within the Spirit of Europeana). This makes our work more difficult.</p>
Czech Republic (NPU)	<p>Our data are online, but they are not in appropriate shape to be ingested. The metadata needed for Europeana are in three or four databases (VAL, ODAN, MonumIS, GIS) which are not connected properly. We need to adjust them first. They have unique identifiers. We provided two other collections during the CARARE project. We have signed the Europeana DEA, IPR will be the same. We established our OAI-PMH repository in the CARARE project which will be used for LoCloud too. We are working on mapping metadata to the CARARE schema (off-line so far).</p>
Denmark (KUAS)	<p>KUAS needs to perform the following tasks before the content is ready for ingestion: 1. Clear IPR In Denmark, most state-subsidised museums, use the Regin tool to catalogue their collections. That is about 100 museums. KUAS supplies the Regin tool, and acts as an aggregator for the metadata and digital assets registered in the system. At the moment, no formal agreement exists between KUAS and the museums that use the Regin tool. Therefore the first task is to reach a formal agreement concerning the intellectual property rights associated with data and metadata in the system. We plan to offer metadata under a CC0 licence, and digital assets under a CC BY licence. This task will be performed during months 9 to 13 of the LoCloud project. That is November 2013 - March 2014. 2. Sign Europeana DEA. Once the agreement on IPR has been finalised, KUAS can sign the DEA. 3. Establish export of metadata - the existing export format from Regin is not suitable for ingestion by the LoCloud aggregator. We will therefore establish a one-time output in a LIDO format. The reason why we will establish a one-time output is that KUAS is building a replacement for Regin. This new system will be ready by 2016. By then we will establish a new export format ready for aggregation by Europeana. This export in LIDO format will be ready for ingestion in month 14 of the LoCloud project – that is April 2014. The export will include: Data from all museums which have entered into an agreement with KUAS about the Regin system. All images which the museums are free to licence under a CC BY licence. We have to exclude all reproductions of works which are still protected by Danish Copyright Law. We will include only works of art where the artist has died before 1944.</p>

Country content provider	Comments
France (CG33)	The content of Archives départementales listed in the DOW content table can also be ingested again by Europeana in the context of the EuropeanaLocal project. We would like to ingest it within the LoCloud project and tools. This is to be checked with Europeana.
Germany (UDE)	UDE identified more than 50 key players (content providers) as potential LoCloud users and external testing partners in Germany in the cultural sector in the Ruhr valley (museums, archives, etc.). Eight organisations are interested in participating in the LoCloud project. We will support them with digitalization, metadata compilation and ingestion to get more content providers. See list in report. Our metadata in XML-EAD is ready, even if we may have information to add for the ESE format. This could be done in the LoCloud mapping tool.
Greece (Future Library)	Future Library is in a unique situation. We are not content providers according to the DoW. Nevertheless, we will try to follow closely all content provider activities and try to implement what is possible from the aforementioned activities in our network of Greek Public Libraries.
Iceland (AHAI)	The dataset of archaeological sites, originally submitted through the CARARE project but with some additional records is available for testing of tools. New content from museum of Skagafjörður will be at the earliest ready by six - seven months. The museum of Skagafjörður is a typical small content provider that needs the means for getting their digital content in order (metadata), online and into a digital repository.
Ireland (DP)	<p><u>Royal Society of Antiquities Ireland (RSAI)</u> - Content including Lantern slide collection & Du Noyer Collection. Digitised content needs to be transferred to the Discovery Programme's Dspace repository and publishing online, IPR needs to be detailed, metadata enriched and URIs allocated, export will be via Dspace. RSAI to sign Europeana DEA.</p> <p><u>Leo Swan Aerial Collection</u> -Content include aerial photographic collection of archaeological sites & monuments. As for RSAI the content will be ingested into the Discovery Programme's Dspace repository. Enrichment of the geodata is planned. Europeana DEA needs to be signed.</p> <p><u>Dublin Institute of Advanced Studies (DIAS)</u> - Content including text, image and 3D models of ogham inscribed stones in Ireland. Content is hosted on DIAS website and is published online; IPR needs detailing; Europeana DEA to be signed, enrichment of metadata with geodata is planned; URIs to be investigated; a means of exporting metadata as XML to be established for metadata mapping via MINT.</p> <p><u>Discovery Programme Image Collection (RSAI)</u> - images of archaeological activities in Ireland. Content needs to be transferred into the DP's Dspace repository and published online, the IPR needs to be cleared, metadata generated and geodata enrichment; export will be via Dspace. The Discovery Programme has signed the Europeana DEA.</p>
Italy (FRS)	We are working on the ingestion of our metadata in Samira, the software for cataloguing provided us by Regione Umbria (following ICCD standards). We foresee the whole digitized material will be ready for the ingestion in Europeana not earlier than six months by now.

Country content provider	Comments
Lithuania (VUKF)	<p>We foresee our content listed in the DOW to be ready for ingestion by LoCloud aggregator at the end of 2014. VUKF needs to perform the following tasks before content would be ready for ingestion: Publish content online (part of it is already published, but not all); Enrich metadata; Provide unique identifiers/URIs; Establish a means to export metadata via OAI/SML/CSV/Other; Map metadata to an intermediary schema (CARARE in ours case); Test content's interoperability with Europeana</p>
Netherlands (RCE)	<p>Content that RCE will provide is partially already online but not all in standard desired metadata.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical Cultural Landscapes (shapefiles): Is accessible online, but data (2005) needs to be reviewed and updated. The required metadata schema is INSPIRE: from there, CARARE schema will be applied. The dataset can be made ready for ingestion in the coming months. • Dataset archaeological reports (21.000 reports in pdf) These reports are available online stored in livelink and metadata in adlib. Available in XML timetable: The dataset can be made ready for ingestion in 2014 • Controlled vocabulary of Dutch archaeology (RNA). This vocabulary is available online, and contains several hundred terms. Which metadata schema to use has to be decided. timetable: The dataset can be made ready for ingestion in the coming months.
Norway (NRA)	<p>NRA will work with different collections. We will also contact new content providers that may find LoCloud services useful.</p> <p>Metadata will be uploaded to LoCloud LDL and Norvegiana may also be used to aggregate and upload metadata.</p> <p>NRA is trying to organize a small group of key players (private archives, private organizations and museums) from regional level and national level to focus on how LoCloud can have a positive effect on competence building, strategic thinking, cooperation and service building on a regional and national level. We have also planned to visit some of the key institutions like the The County Archive of Sogn og Fjordane and the Archive of Vestfold.</p>
Poland (PSNC)	<p>PSNC will work only with the collection of Teatr NN which was already described in previous action planning and metadata survey. In order to share the collection DEA needs to signed. Metadata are available through OAI-PMH interface and can harvested by Polish Digital Libraries Federation at any time. It is hard to estimate effort necessary to perform mapping because it depends from intermediary schema which will be finally chosen. When this would be decided we will estimate effort necessary to perform this operation. As these metadata are quite simple it shouldn't be very problematic.</p>
Portugal (FMNF)	<p>We are planning our metadata will be ready for ingestion during the second semester 2014. We are now working with two different situations: 1. Metadata from the archive collection – This collection was already online and only would need metadata mapping to an intermediary schema (EAD). Unfortunately, our archive software is presenting several technical problems. At present, we do not have our archive content accessible online. FMNF is working on a solution for this situation. 2. Metadata from the museum collection – For this collection we are working in publish content online and metadata enrichment. We will also need to map metadata to an intermediary schema, likely LIDO. Content will be ready to ingestion during the second semester 2014.</p>

Country content provider	Comments
Romania (BJC)	The content providers included in DoW have the digital content but not metadata associated. During 2014 we will assure assistance for metadata creation, but at this point we need to establish which schema to use ESE or EDM?
Serbia (BGB)	We suppose our metadata will be ready until the end of 2014. Our data are online, but they are not in appropriate shape to be ingested. We need to adjust them first. They have unique identifiers.
Slovakia (PrifUK KAEG)	Most of the metadata for the content listed in the DoW will be ready for ingestion until June/July 2014. We will need the training session for MINT mentioned at Copenhagen meeting.
Slovenia (Zavad Jara) (IPCHS)	<p>KAMRA is already the aggregator of the content, participated by small local institutions. KAMRA's editors in Slovenian regions continuously approach local museums, associations, public libraries, schools to publish their digital content. If institutions don't have equipment and capacity to digitise material, it is digitised and uploaded by nearby public libraries. Public Library Celje, that manages KAMRA, signed the DEA with Europeana and all content providers have to accept the conditions described in DEA.</p> <p>IPCHS will make available two collections, the Archaeological Research database and the Restoration database of works of art. The content and metadata of the archaeological database are under review, there maybe copyright issues with some objects, but it is anticipated that the collection will be ready for ingestion during 2015. The Restoration database requires some improvements to existing metadata; it is anticipated that this collection will be ready for ingestion in winter 2014-spring 2015.</p>
Spain (MECD)	47 potential content providers have been identified and contacted up to now. 34 of them are interested in participating. They are at very different stages ranging from seven museums + one library that could be ready for ingestion by April 2014 to institutions where all the tasks listed above, apart from publish content online, need to be done.
Sweden (ABMR)	We have to import, enrich and publish metadata from our content providers. Then we need to transform the metadata from the SPECTRUM-fields to LIDO for ingestion into the LoCloud aggregator. We plan to have this done before the end of 2014
Turkey (HU)	Hacettepe University, Department of Information Management has experience as the content aggregator by ingesting 50 thousand cultural heritage assets of Turkey in Europeana. Topics like digitization, digital libraries, metadata enrichment and metadata mapping are main research interests of project members. The Vehbi Koç and Ankara Research Center (VEKAM) will sign the DEA with Europeana and they have a local institutional repository, called MIDAS digital archiving system (available at: http://95.9.73.68:8081/) and their information objects were described according to DCMES. In this context, we will need metadata enrichment and revise conditions on publishing content online since VEKAM provides restricted content access. According to our program, the metadata will be ready for ingestion.

Country content provider	Comments
United Kingdom (UoY ADS)	<p>Grey Literature Library: The GLL, which consists primarily of PDF/A files of unpublished archaeological field reports, has already been published successfully in Europeana through the CARARE project. For LoCloud, we will provide an updated set of metadata, as the GLL has now grown by a further 3,000 reports. These reports are ready for ingestion now, and will only require an update to the existing mapping to CARARE, to reflect any updates in the CARARE 2.0 schema. ADS archived collections resource discovery metadata: ADS will provide resource discovery metadata for all 450+ of its existing collections. All ADS archives have metadata mapped to the ADS archive schema (extended Dublin Core with geospatial data for most), and are ready for ingestion now. Proceedings of the Society of Antiquaries of Scotland (PSAS): ADS will provide metadata for the c. 4000 PSAS reports, dating from 1851 to the present. PSAS has Dublin Core metadata, and are ready for ingestion now. The list above reflects what ADS will provide according to DoW.</p> <p>With the exception of the Grey Literature Library, which has already been mapped to CARARE 1.0.6.2, all will need to be mapped to CARARE 2.0.</p>

3. Additional content providers

In this section partners describe additional content metadata sources, not listed in the DoW, which may potentially be ingested in LoCloud.

Country Content provider	Comments
Austria (AIT)	Year 2013: Our yearly conference “Digitale Bibliothek” that takes place in Graz in November 2013 will be the starting point for aggregating and approaching new partners in Austria (average number of conference attendees: 100 persons from across Austria and neighbouring countries). Year 2014: We will approach the regional museums network (MUSIS, http://www.musis.at) as an accelerator and other local cultural heritage institutions directly. Furthermore we will approach new partners via our network of cultural institutions engaged in the organisation of the “Digitale Bibliothek” (eg. University of Graz, Vienna and Innsbruck). The “Digitale Bibliothek 2014” shall include a specialised LoCloud workshop.
Belgium (Provincie Limburg)	No additional content sources were specifically identified by the partner.
Bulgaria (PSRL)	We will work mainly with institutions (libraries and museums) which have not presented their content online yet. We will try to extend the content related with monuments and any other museums’ artifacts.
Croatia (GKR)	We will contact majority of local institutions in cultural sector, like smaller libraries and some museums. We will also approach other civil initiatives – like NGOs or small private museums.
Cyprus (CUT)	For reasons like the very bad financial situation in Cyprus, risk management and in order to reach our objectives to deliver the planned number of objects, we decided to inform all CY stakeholders and ask for their cooperation. Therefore, we are focusing –at the moment– on the local stakeholders of the city of Limassol. A second phase awareness campaign has been planned in December. This is in cooperation with the Ministry of Education and Culture. We are planning to finalise our list of CH stakeholders by the end of February 2014.

Country Content provider	Comments
Czech Republic (NPU)	<p>We will focus on architecture and archaeology area. (Data of moveable monuments are very strictly protected in our institution, they are not public. There are other institutions which play the role of aggregators for Europeana , e.g. the National Library and the National Museum, in our country.) We intend to approach some institutions and NGOš which are interested in architecture: SOVAMM - Společnost pro obnovu vesnice a malého města: http://sovamm.wz.cz/english.htm; Ústav dějin umění http://www.udu.cas.cz/en/, http://www.udu.cas.cz/cs/oddeleni-topografie/; Muzeum města Brna http://www.spilberk.cz/?lang=en; Národní technické museum http://www.ntm.cz/en/en-archiv-knihovna/archiv-architektury. In our opinion the timetable partly depends on development of the lightweight library and other tools. It will be easier to persuade new content providers with offer of concrete tools which can be shown. We can do it in the second and especially in the third year of the project. There are more potential sources of metadata. We can approach them via e-mails or via our web site, perhaps personally. In our opinion timetable partly depends on development of the lightweight library and other tools. It will be easier to persuade new content providers with offer of concrete tools which can be shown. We can do it in the second and especially in the third year of the project.</p>
Denmark (KUAS)	<p>KUAS will not approach other content provider institutions.</p>
France (CG33)	<p>CG33 is approaching potential new content provider institutions.</p>
Germany (UDE)	<p>UDE, as a not content or service provider, identified more than 50 key players (content providers) as potential LoCloud users and external testing partners in Germany in the cultural sector in the Ruhr valley (museums, archives, etc.). Eight organisations are interested in participating in the LoCloud project. We will support them with digitalization, metadata compilation and ingestion to get more content providers.</p>
Greece (Future Library)	<p>There is a significant number of institutions which can potentially be approached by the Greek partners of LoCloud. These include about 80 Greek cultural Organisations which have recently completed the ENUMERATE questionnaire. Moreover, in January 2014 starts Greek Presidency of EU and there will be 2-3 official Conferences and 2-3 more Cultural Conferences which will be organised until June 2014. It will be possible to approach these Content Providers in the framework of the events to be organised as well.</p> <p>Nine Greek Public Libraries (Drama, Kozani, Trikala, Levadia, Korinth, Naupaktos, Keratsini-Drapetsona, Ilioupoli, Chania) will be approached. These libraries will have a brand new media lab in the end of the year 2013. http://medialab.futurelibrary.gr/wp-content/uploads/2013/09/banner-english.pdf</p>
Iceland (AHAI)	<p>We have focused on local institutions in the municipality of Skagafjörður and have already approached them. Most of them will not participate because of cost and copyright issues but the local museum of Skagafjörður have decided to take part in the project.</p>

Country Content provider	Comments
Ireland (DP)	<p>1 Representative Church Body Library - Range of church documents including: digitised copies of church newspaper. Content is already online via their own repository. Assessment of additional activities required e.g. URI. DEA will be carried out once initial meetings take place.</p> <p>2 Members of AARG (Aerial Archaeology Research Group) who maintain private collections of aerial photographs of archaeological sites. Discussion already taken place at this year's AARG meeting in Amersfoort, Netherlands. Follow up with contact individual members. Assessment of additional activities required e.g. URI. DEA will be carried out once initial meetings take place.</p>
Italy (FRS)	FRS did not identify any new content providing partners. It is supporting communications with House Museums in Europe that may be interested in participating in LoCloud.
Lithuania (VUKF)	Only those mentioned in the DoW: the Society of the Lithuanian Archeology and "DIZI heritage" (both already approached).
Netherlands (RCE)	<p>Institutes for which RCE acts as aggregator:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional/local museums: metadata probably via DimCon. • Archaeological depot of province of Gelderland: part of its collection is available online, metadata schema not standard. • Other archaeological depots and museums (not present in DiMCoN) have to be contacted. A database of heritage organizations is available. A timetable for approaching other content provider institutions (additional to the ones in the DoW content table) is not available yet. <p>But we have started approaching potential content providers and intend to continue that process in the coming months.</p>
Norway (NRA)	<p>NRA will work with different collections as already described in previous action planning and metadata survey. We will also contact new content providers that may find LoCloud services useful. Metadata will be uploaded to LoCloud LDL. Norvegiana may also be used to aggregate and upload metadata at any time.</p> <p>NRA is trying to organize a small group of key players (private archives, private organizations and museums) from regional level and national level to focus on how LoCloud can have a positive effect on competence building, strategic thinking, cooperation and service building on a regional and national level. We have also planned to visit some of the key institutions like the County Archive of Sogn og Fjordane and the Archive of Vestfold.</p>
Poland (PSNC)	No new content providing institutions were identified by PSNC.

Country Content provider	Comments
Portugal (FMNF)	<p>We are focusing on railway heritage but also on local and regional content providers. We have been inviting several institutions to join us. For now, we have three but we still need to confirm the real state of the art of their metadata. The institutions are the following:</p> <p>REFER – Heritage Department; Municipality of Abrantes; Municipality of Vila Nova de Famalicão.</p> <p>For these three institutions timetable is second semester of 2014. As we are focusing on railway heritage, these kinds of collections are mainly propriety of individuals. To approach them we need to have LDL solution tested. Timetable for this depends on the development of LDL.</p>
Romania (BJC)	Small local libraries in Cluj County will provide their content in 2014-2015.
Serbia (BGB)	In our opinion timetable partly depends on development of the lightweight library and other tools. It will be easier to persuade new content providers with offer of concrete tools which can be shown. We can do it in the second and especially in the third year of the project.
Slovakia (PrifUK KAEG)	There are more potential sources of metadata. We can approach them via e-mails or via our web site, perhaps personally.
Slovenia (Zavad Jara)	KAMRA's editors in Slovenian regions continuously approach local museums, associations, public libraries, schools to publish their digital content. If institutions don't have equipment and capacity to digitise material, it is digitised and uploaded by nearby public libraries.
Spain (MECD)	47 potential content providers have been identified and contacted up to now. 34 of them are interested in participating. They are at very different stages ranging from seven museums + one library that could be ready for ingestion by April 2014 to institutions where all the tasks listed above, apart from publish content online, need to be done.
Sweden (ABMR)	Our new content providers are: Film i Västernorrland, June 2014, Näringslivsarkivet I Norrland, August 2014, Styrnäs hembygdsförening, August 2014
Turkey (HU)	The Vehbi Koç and Ankara Research Center (VEKAM - http://vekam.org.tr/index.php?dil=en&page=home) is the content provider for Turkey. We are working on the metadata.

Country Content provider	Comments
United Kingdom (UoY ADS)	<p>We have identified the specific archives below, which include holdings from small to medium sized organisations. All are ready for ingestion now.</p> <p>Star Carr Archive: ADS will provide metadata for around 2,500 artefacts (most with images, but not all) held in the following museums: British Museum, Hull and East Riding Museum, Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology, Cambridge Natural History Museum, National Museum of Ireland</p> <p>Scarborough Museum, Whitby Museum, Yorkshire, Yorkshire Museum, York. Wessex Archaeology Image Archive: ADS will provide metadata for this collection totalling about 300 images from the following small museums/county archives: Salisbury and South Wiltshire Museum</p> <p>Wiltshire Heritage, Hampshire County Council, Wiltshire Council. Southampton Museum's Archive:</p> <p>The ADS will provide metadata for these collections, totaling about 424 images (and reports in PDF, CAD plans in DXF and a variety of other file types) from the Southampton City Council. ADS has convened its planning group, which consists of members of our Management Committee, members of the Forum on Information Standards in Heritage (FISH), and members of Historic Environment Information Resources Network (HEIRNET).</p> <p>We have asked these members in turn to make contact with any small and medium sized organisations with whom they work to determine if they are interested in participating in LoCloud. We have already had early interest from the Worcestershire Archive and Archaeology Service, and Cambridgeshire County Council. ADS will follow up with the members of the FISH-HEIRNET meeting in November.</p>

4. Politics of aggregation

Thirteen countries are represented by LoCloud partners which already act as aggregators of content metadata either for a single domain or cross-domain. In other cases discussions are required with existing aggregators to clarify the role of LoCloud. In several countries there is no aggregator for local and regionally-sourced metadata.

Fig 2 Consortium partners which are aggregators of local/regional content

Country Content provider	Comments
Austria (AIT)	We are the regional and local aggregator, established as an outcome of the EuropeanaLocal project.
Belgium (Provincie Limburg)	We are a regional aggregator ourselves (cross-domain, currently covering two Belgian provinces). We cannot make a parallel service to our own system and services, so we must find how the LoCloud modules can be integrated with our own in a complementary way.
Bulgaria (PSRL)	Since PSRL is an aggregator there is no conflict with other aggregators.
Croatia (GKR)	We will need to discuss aggregation with the National and University Library in Zagreb and the Ministry of Culture

Country Content provider	Comments
Cyprus (CUT)	We are working closely with the Ministry of Education and Culture. Sustainability of the LoCloud Project after the end of the project (who is going to run the Cloud services, the preservation of the metadata and under which costs?). Please have in mind that these are the most common questions which we are receiving from the CY stakeholders. The financial situation in Cyprus is very bad and they don't want to undertake any future commitments and risks.
Czech Republic (NPU)	There is no other regional aggregator in the architecture and archaeology area. There could be established a national aggregator for the Czech Republic during the project. Probably it will not happen.
Denmark (KUAS)	We will need to discuss the work of LoCloud with the National Library of Denmark, which is the national aggregator. We foresee no problems.
France (CG33)	We can discuss it with the BNSA, a regional aggregator which ought to deliver content to Europeana via the French national aggregator culture.fr. For the moment they do not deliver archival collections to Europeana. Moreover, the national aggregator in archival matter is not yet defined, the internet portal of the " Archives de France" is being developed.
Germany	UDE, as a not content or service provider, identified more than 50 key players (content providers) as potential LoCloud users and external testing partners in Germany in the cultural sector in the Ruhr valley (museums, archives, etc.). Eight organisations are interested in participating in the LoCloud project. We will support them with digitalization, metadata compilation and ingestion to get more content providers and by working with the German national library in Frankfurt.
Greece	Existing nominal aggregators include: 1) Hellenic Aggregator for Europeana, Veria Public Library, http://aggregator.libver.gr/ (established in Europeana Local) 2) The National Documentation Center (Ministry of Culture) 3) Plans for a new national aggregator at the National Library (Ministry of Education), which will incorporate 1)
Iceland (AHAI)	There are no local or regional aggregator services but we will consult the National Museum of Iceland. We have to find a way to keep the project alive after the LoCloud project has come to an end. We have to keep that in mind when we choose a method of for example publishing content online.
Ireland (DP)	Currently in Ireland the Irish Manuscripts Commission (IMC) are the national aggregator for Europeana. Contact has been made with this institution on the process and policy of them acting as regional aggregator. Their services are available to institutions funded by the Department of Arts, Heritage & Gaeltacht, which the Discovery Programme is. Once decision taken to utilise IMC services formal request will be sent to Manager Cathy Hayes. The aggregation of the DIAS data will need to be explored as they are directly funded by a different government department. Firstly the IMC will be asked. If this is not possible aggregation may have to take place at a project level and their metadata ingestion requirements will be implemented. No risk is foreseen. If IMC is selected a detailed report of all proposed content will be provided to them so they can incorporate any additional efforts into their 2014-2015 planning.

Country Content provider	Comments
Italy (FRS)	We need to discuss about LoCloud with Regione Umbria, AIB (Associazione Italiana Biblioteche), MAB Umbria (Musei-Archivi-Biblioteche).
Lithuania (VUKF)	We don't need to approach the national aggregator for LoCloud project.
Netherlands (RCE)	There are several services and tools to help /contribute or may conflict with the LoCloud services and tools. RCE has developed the Erfgoed suite which is a tool to provide content on line for small and medium sized cultural institutes. Another service is the Erfgoedthesaurus combines knowledge through key vocabularies. Services (Sip-creator) have been developed to map and upload collection metadata to DiMCoN (and from there to put it through to Europeana) It might conflict with the role and position of the national aggregator if it is bypassed by heritage organizations directly delivering content to Europeana. A second risk is the existence of two toolsets to map, improve and deliver metadata to Europeana.
Norway (NRA)	Norvegiana is serving aggregation of regional and local content for museums and archives. We can't see any risk and the cooperation works well. Semantic enrichment is discussed at several levels in Norway and may be focused within the framework of LoCloud too.
Poland (PSNC)	PSNC is an operator of Polish Digital Libraries Federation depending on project requirements we can contribute metadata of objects mentioned in the DOW through LoCloud infrastructure or directly to Europeana.
Portugal (FMNF)	In Portugal it is needed to discuss the work of LoCloud with three "sectors" thematic aggregators: National Library, the national aggregator for library collections; General Directorate for Cultural Heritage, the national aggregator for museums collections; National Archive (belongs to the General Directorate for the Book, Archives and Libraries), the national aggregator for archives collection. All the three national aggregators were informed by e-mail about LoCloud since the beginning. We met with National Library General Director and we agreed on the following work methodology: we will not aggregate metadata from library collections and will make the link through the Library potential content provider and the National Library. We also agreed to keep National Library informed on cloud technological developments. Still no answers from the national aggregators for archives and museums.
Romania (BJC)	The Institute for Cultural Memory is the National aggregator according to a Governmental decision no. HG 1676/2008. This legal document contains also the Public Policy for Digitisation of National Cultural Resources and Creation of Romanian Digital Library.
Serbia (BGB)	There is no national or regional aggregator available.
Slovakia (PrifUK KAEG)	We will discuss concerning LoCloud with Slovenský národný archív.
Slovenia (Zavad Jara) (IPCHS)	Kamra is a Europeana aggregator, so there is no conflict with other aggregators. Further discussion is needed regarding ingestion by the LoCloud aggregator. IPCHS is the national agency for the protection of the protection of the cultural heritage in Slovenia and is making available its own collections.

Country Content provider	Comments
Spain (MECD)	MECD manages the Spanish national cross domain aggregator. Duplications must be avoided so that it's necessary to find the way in order not to duplicate processes.
Sweden (ABMR)	Regional aggregator in Västernorrland is our regional cultural heritage portal "Kulturav Västernorrland" and Murberget Läns museet Västernorrland. We manage our regional aggregator within our organization.
Turkey (HU)	Over the past (and first also in Europeana from Turkey) experience of Hacettepe University as an aggregator in AccessIT Project, we will work and discuss on sharing processes in LoCloud again with the team of Hacettepe University.
United Kingdom (UoY ADS)	ADS will focus on the Historic Environment Records, and Sites and Monuments Records, as museums in the UK are part of the Europeana Inside project, led by the Collections Trust.

5. Intermediate Metadata Schema

Partners expressed a preference to use the following as intermediate or 'pivot' schema for mapping to EDM in the following number of instances (see also D1.3):

CARARE	9	
EAD	4	
EDM	10	
LIDO	12	
Other	2	
None specified/unsure	5	MARC 21; ABM Semantic Elements Norway

Country of partner	Preferred schema	Comments
Austria (AIT)	EDM	We will provide the aggregated data in EDM schema, and will support the knowledge about EDM among our content providing institutions.
Belgium (Provincie Limburg)	LIDO	LIDO is the closest to the type of content we have most of at this moment.
Bulgaria (PSRL)	EDM	At the moment all metadata are mapped to ESE format but they can to move to EDM in few months.
Croatia (GKR)	EDM	Since we come from the library sector we envisage to promote and support EDM among content provider institutions. Dublin Core, DCTerms, UNIMARC and MARC 21 are mostly used as metadata schemas in library sector and we wish to have EDM support integrated in local systems from the start.
Cyprus (CUT)	-	The stakeholders need to decide about it. We are explaining to them the advantages and disadvantages. For us the most important issue is the quality of the metadata: to have the complete and detail object information included in the metadata.
Czech Republic (NPU)	CARARE	
Denmark (KUAS)	LIDO	We will use the LIDO schema as intermediary schema. However, the content provider institutions need not be involved in this.
France (CG33)	-	

Country of partner	Preferred schema	Comments
Germany	-	No idea yet, as no experience in this field. Perhaps we can propose potential partners from Germany to follow metadata format restrictions of the DDB. https://www.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/content/faq/#E130 : Admissible input formats are Dublin Core, MODS/METS, MARC21, EAD (-DDB) and LIDO. Data should be delivered in XML format, as they will be converted using XSLT-based transformers to the internal format of the DDB. If the formats mentioned above cannot be supplied, the DDB competence network provides help with converting the existing format in each case to one of the required standard formats.
Greece	CARARE, LIDO, EDM	Depending on the content provided.
Iceland (AHAI)	CARARE, LIDO, EAD, EDM	We have mostly promoted CARARE but we might have a quick look at LIDO
Ireland (DP)	CARARE	We will promote both the CARARE metadata schema and the EDM within the project. CARARE has been chosen as this is most suitable for the content provided.
Italy (FRS)	LIDO	It depends by the nature of the institutions. Usually we have contacts with house museums and similar institutions which preserve art collections. According to the recent deliverables about intermediary schemas, we think that the best schema to promote among content providers as house museum would be LIDO.
Lithuania (VUKF)	CARARE	We are planning to use CARARE as intermediary schema, which we think is best suited for archaeological content.
Netherlands (RCE)	CARARE, LIDO, EDM	Geographical information should be set up according INSPIRE Guidelines (required for site/ monuments that are legally protected).
Norway (NRA)	CARARE, LIDO, EAD, EDM, ABM Semantic elements Norway	
Poland (PSNC)	LIDO	
Portugal (FMNF)	EAD (Archives collection), LIDO (Museums collection)	FMNF still would like to discuss with LoCloud colleagues the need of intermediate metadata schemas

Country of partner	Preferred schema	Comments
Romania (BJC)	-	We are now using ESE. We want to use any other schema that the LoCloud IT specialist will suggest for libraries.
Serbia (BGB)	-	We are now using DC simple. We are willing to consider any other schema that the LoCloud IT will suggest.
Slovakia (PrifUK KAEG)	CARARE, LIDO	
Slovenia (Zavad Jara)	EDM	At the moment we are mapping Kamra's metadata to ESE, but we plan to move to EDM in a few months.
Spain (MECD)	LIDO, EDM, MARC21	
Sweden (ABMR)	LIDO, EAD, EDM	
Turkey (HU)	EDM	We will promote Dublin Core format of the content and we suppose that we can also create ESE and EDM formats.
United Kingdom (UoY ADS)	CARARE	CARARE will be appropriate for the metadata we hold, and the metadata we may aggregate from other institutions.

6. Infrastructure testing

Asked whether they would be willing or interested to carry out testing of cloud-based infrastructure tools as envisaged in the workplan, partners responded positively in the following number of instances.

MINT	12
MORE	12
LDL	13
Crawler-friendly tagging	1
Other ingestion methods	2

Country of partner	Tools willing to test	Nominated individuals	Comments
Austria (AIT)	MINT, MORE, LDL		
Belgium (Provincie Limburg)	LDL		We think that the LDL can offer a solution to some potential data providers that our current system does not cover. Before we ask them to participate, we intend to test the LDL thoroughly ourselves, with content that is similar to that of those possible local providers.
Bulgaria (PSRL)	LDL		
Croatia (GKR)	MINT, MORE, LDL		
Cyprus (CUT)	MINT, MORE		CUT is willing to test MINT and MORE using CY metadata/objects. We cannot make any commitment about the last two options, due to the fact that we need more detail information.
Czech Republic (NPU)	MORE	Petr Volfik in cooperation with our external technical support (ANECT)	

Country of partner	Tools willing to test	Nominated individuals	Comments
Denmark (KUAS)	MINT	Kristine Hoff Meyer	KUAS could participate in testing MINT. However, our data will be supplied in a LIDO format, so we will not need the mapping part.
France (CG33)	LDL	Julien Dutertre will coordinate the tests with the librarian department.	We will be utilising both MORE & MINT tools. We would also like to explore the harvesting of metadata from website content for the DIAS collection data. For the aerial images we intend to deposit within the project we would like to explore the use of the LDL.
Germany (UDE)			UDE will work with the National Library in Frankfurt, which is interested in testing microservices when they become available.
Greece (Future Library)	LDL, MORE		NTUA will be involved in “cloud based metadata preparation tools (e.g. MINT)”
Iceland (AHAI)	MINT, MORE, LDL		AHAI in cooperation with the local museum of Skagafjörður are ready to test MINT, MORE, Lightweight Digital Library. Difficult to say about other methods of ingestion beforehand – we need a little more info.
Ireland (DP)	MINT, MORE, LDL, Other ingestion methods	Anthony Corns and colleagues	We will be utilising both MORE & MINT tools. We would also like to explore the harvesting of metadata from website content for the DIAS collection data. For the aerial images we intend to deposit within the project we would like to explore the use of the LDL.
Italy (FRS)	MINT, LDL		
Lithuania (VUKF)	MINT, MORE	Mantas Bardas, Rimvydas Laužikas, Ingrida Vosyliūtė	

Country of partner	Tools willing to test	Nominated individuals	Comments
Netherlands (RCE)	MINT, MORE, LDL	Hans Schraven, Will Brouwers, Bart Broex	Based on the CARARE experience, RCE will use MINT and MORE (for the cultural landscapes and archaeological datasets), and SIPCreator for museums and other heritage institutes concerned with movable cultural heritage. Lightweight Digital Library may be used for text documents (depending on test results).
Norway (NRA)	MINT, MORE, Crawler-friendly metadata tagging, Other methods of ingestion		
Poland (PSNC)	-		
Portugal (FMNF)	LDL		
Romania (BJC)	LDL		
Serbia (BGB)	LDL		
Slovakia (PrifUK KAEG)	MINT		
Slovenia (Zavad Jara)	-		We will not be involved in lightweight cloud infrastructure. But if it shows up that we can do any useful work as an independent aggregator, we are willing to be a part. We need to test different solutions in order to be able to decide. We use CollectiveAccess as database, the MINT- tool for preparation and REPOX for aggregation.
Spain (MECD)	All		
Sweden (ABMR)			
Turkey (HU)	MINT, MORE, LDL	Dr. Özgür Külcü and Tolga Çakmak	

Country of partner	Tools willing to test	Nominated individuals	Comments
United Kingdom (UoY ADS)	MINT, MORE	Holly Wright	

7. Microservice (SaaS) testing

Partners indicated willingness to be involved in testing the LoCloud microservices in the following number of instances.

Geolocation enrichment	16
Historic place names	12
Vocabularies and languages	11
Metadata enrichment	13
Wikimedia/crowdsourcing	11

Country of partner	Microservice willing to test	Nominated individual	Comments
Austria (AIT)	All	Gerda Koch	We also plan to approach regional and local content providers for dedicated testing.
Belgium (Provincie Limburg)	Geolocation enrichment Metadata Enrichment Vocabularies and languages Historic place names		Seven years after implementation of our thesaurus and ontology management system (SKOS & OWL), we are currently rebuilding it with more recent technology, and with improvements based on the 7-years experience. This experience will be useful for testing the various thesaurus- and placenames-related microservices.
Bulgaria (PSRL)	Geolocation enrichment Metadata enrichment.	Radka Kalcheva	
Croatia (GKR)	All		
Cyprus (CUT)	All		
Czech Republic (NPU)	Geolocation enrichment	Zuzana Syrova	Our data has geolocation.
Denmark (KUAS)	Wikimedia/crowd sourcing	Kristine Hoff Meyer	KUAS is not immediately interested in using any of the microservices.
France (CG33)	-		

Country of partner	Microservice willing to test	Nominated individual	Comments
Germany	-		
Greece (Future Library)	All		As a research partner NTUA will be involved in activities such as Geolocation enrichment tools, Metadata Enrichment
Iceland (AHAÍ)	Metadata enrichment Vocabularies and languages Wikimedia/crowd sourcing.		CHAI in cooperation with the local museum of Skagafjörður would like to be involved
Ireland (DP)	Geolocation enrichment Vocabularies and languages	Anthony Corns	
Italy (FRS)	All		
Lithuania (VUKF)	Geolocation enrichment Vocabularies and languages Historic place names	Rimvydas Laužikas, Vykintas Vaitkevičius, Ingrida Vosyliūtė.	
Netherlands (RCE)	All		In addition, for accessing/viewing/querying the geographical data, using options such as OpenLayers or MapNik (or other) is preferred.
Norway (NRA)	All		
Poland (PSNC)			PSNC will focus mainly on Wikimedia/crowd sourcing app. The rest of the services should be used as a part of LDL.
Portugal (FMNF)	Geolocation enrichment		
Romania (BJC)			We cannot test this application at this moment.

Country of partner	Microservice willing to test	Nominated individual	Comments
Serbia (BGB)	Historic place names Wikimedia/crowd sourcing.		
Slovakia (PrifUK KAEG)	Historic place names		
Slovenia (Zavad Jara)	Geolocation enrichment Metadata enrichment	Breda Karun in cooperation with developer of Kamra	After testing we would like to include these services in Kamra. It might be an example of testing these tools in external aggregator. As for Wikimedia/crowd sourcing we need more information to decide if Kamra is a possible environment for testing.
Spain (MECD)	-		
Sweden (ABMR)	All		
Turkey (HU)	All		Since VEKAM is a research center which collects and organizes information objects about Ankara, every microservice testing element is important for us.
United Kingdom (UoY ADS)	Geolocation enrichment Metadata enrichment Vocabularies and languages.	Holly Wright	

8. Online training

Partners described the 'market or nature of the demand for the online training envisaged in WP4 in the following terms:

Country of partner	Market for online training
Austria (AIT)	The main target group for the online training course are small, private and public, local and regional institutions and collectors. We would promote the course on our EuropeanLocal Website (probably also translate the course, if feasible), we could include information on the course on our national folders, at conferences etc...We would talk to our regional museums network and distribute the information to the Austrian (university and public) libraries and archives networks.
Belgium (Provincie Limburg)	Local collection holders or members of associations who have large amounts of objects that are poorly documented (e.g. photographs, images). They need a good, reliable and cheap system for documenting their collection and sharing it (or a selection) on the web. Participating in the meetings of their own communication platforms. Local heritage support institutions who intend to build an image bank with images provided by the public, and intend to use them to show the 'identity' and history of their region.
Bulgaria (PSRL)	New data providers are the main target group for online training courses. The course will be promoted primarily by invitations for any potential participant – emails and personal talks.
Croatia (GKR)	Students of LIS, professionals working at content provider institutions, general librarian community. Wide range of institutions and professionals
Cyprus (CUT)	All those CY stakeholders, who will be included in our final list (February 2014). Of course our staff also.
Czech Republic (NPU)	It is still only possibility we will gain additional content providers. These new content providers are the target group. We will use our website and e-mails.
Denmark (KUAS)	Kristine Hoff Meyer from KUAS will need to be able to use the LoCloud aggregation service.
France (CG33)	The target group will be archive's IT team and local partners.
Germany	We will need training for LoCloud aggregation service and MINT. Also new content providers will definitely need training. We need to talk mostly personally to potential participants.

Country of partner	Market for online training
Greece (NTUA) (Future Library)	Starting from the ENUMERATE cultural heritage institution list and other lists held by the Hellenic Ministry of Culture. The target of the training would be: a) Some of the personnel of Future Library. b) Librarians of the 9 Greek Public Libraries supported by Future Library (Drama, Kozani, Trikala, Levadia, Korinth, Naupaktos, Keratsini-Drapetsona, Ilioupoli, Chania). There is no problem ensuring support for this.
Iceland (AHAI)	Mainly staff of CHAI and the local museum of Skagafjörður but we will invite other local institutes, especially if there will be some kind of introduction.
Ireland (DP)	The online training course will be aimed at the staff at the various institutions providing the data & metadata to Europeana. The course will be promoted and explained via a series of small briefings and workshops. Liaise with each institution to identify a suitable time and location for briefing/workshop.
Italy (FRS)	We will promote the course among small and medium institutions by using our website and social network. We need to talk with regional institutions as Regione Umbria, MAB Umbria, which could support the promotion of the course.
Lithuania (VUKF)	Online training could be useful for all VUKF personnel working in LoCloud project. Additionally, we could share information about the course with other Lithuanian institutions that are involved in other Europeana projects (via e-mail, VUKF webpage, social media channels, etc.).
Netherlands (RCE)	We will establish the need for training with the heritage organizations that will join us in LoCloud. These are all part of our main target group. We will talk to our contacts with the interested heritage organizations about the online training.
Norway (NRA)	All Norwegian stakeholders (local institutions in different regions of Norway), who will be included in our final list (February 2014) and of course colleagues at NRA that are interested. Need to talk to, to ensure maximum interest and support for this: Arts Council of Norway and directly to some local institutions.
Poland (PSNC)	As we are supposed to develop these trainings we would like to wait at the responses from other partners. Since 2009 we are running courses developed in AccessIT and AccessITplus on a regular basis.
Portugal (FMNF)	We prepared a small web survey that will be sent in a couple of days to professionals from archives, museums and libraries. We hope that this survey results help us to know the potential “clients” for online course. We will promote the course using our website and facebook profile as well as e-mail dissemination We will request for help to National Library, National Archive and General Directorate for Cultural Heritage. We will also request for help in dissemination to the Portuguese Association of Librarians and Archivists.
Romania (BJC)	IT specialist from all county libraries and national content providers will be the target group. We will promote the course on line on librarians’ mailing list. With directors of all public libraries and national content providers.

Country of partner	Market for online training
Serbia (BGB)	We will promote the course among small and medium institutions by using our website, social network and professional mailing lists. Serbian national center for digitisation.
Slovakia (PrifUK KAEG)	We will need training for LoCloud aggregation service and MINT. Also new content providers will need training. We need to talk mostly personally to potential participants.
Slovenia (Zavad Jara)	Depends on the situation we are interested on training on geolocation enrichment and metadata enrichment tools and possible Wikimedia/crowd sourcing. Target group is Kamra's development team
Spain (MECD)	As we foresee a large group of participants, the main target group is the staff of MECD. Then MECD will address training of stakeholders.
Sweden (ABMR)	Both the working group and the content partners need training and support for services and tools developed in LoCloud, on different levels. The main target group will be the working group.
Turkey (HU)	We have reached more than 500 participants in the digitization education that is the most crowded online distance education application in LIS in Turkey. In WP4, our target group will be individuals who work in small and medium scaled cultural heritage institutions. We can also promote this course as OER material by supporting lifelong learning and we can reach more different groups who would like to benefit from this kind of education. There are two major professional associations in Turkey. They are Turkish Library Association (TLA) and University and Research Librarians' Association (URLA). We will keep in touch with their managerial boards and they have some branches located in different cities in Turkey. We will use professional and local discussion lists, namely known as of UNAK and KUTUP-L, for increasing interest and support.
United Kingdom (UoY ADS)	As discussed in the York workshop, it has been clearly communicated to us from the potential participants contacted through our planning group, most do not have interest or resources beyond making their data ready for export, and the time and effort required to learn to use the infrastructure will not be available. As such, we expect to use the expertise gained in the CARARE project and in preparing our own metadata for ingest (and our many years of experience working with depositors), to do the work within the ADS. We do not have a main target group for online training.

9. Conclusions

The majority of content provider partners are planning to have their **metadata available for ingestion** by the LoCloud aggregator before the end of 2014. In some other cases clarification and support is needed by the partners responsible for the overall ingestion process. In a few cases, there is a need for further discussion of the role and extent of metadata provision to the LoCloud aggregator, in view of the existing aggregation pipeline to Europeana in that country.

A substantial number of **content sources in addition to those described in the DOW** have been identified by country partners. It is probable that this number will increase as LoCloud proceeds. Availability of the Lightweight Digital Library is seen as pre-requisite to approaching smaller institutions about their online content by a number of partners. Attention will be required to the scheduling of preparation and ingestion of this metadata, in view of the commitment to make available to Europeana the content listed in the DoW and to meet the Year 3 KPI of 3 million items.

An acceptable basis has been established for the use of **intermediate or 'pivot' metadata schemas** between partners' native schemas and EDM. A number of partners wish to use or map directly to EDM. Whilst mappings are available from CARARE and LIDO, further work is needed clarify the position for EDM and to define what is needed by libraries and other small institutions currently Dublin Core simple, especially when additional content providers, beyond those listed in the DOW, come on stream.

There is more than sufficient interest among partners in being involved in the **testing** of both the cloud-based infrastructure components and the microservices (SaaS). This will need to be distributed rationally. There may be need to promote more interest in testing crawler-friendly tagging and other novel ingestion methods, although these responses were obtained before the presentation on the subject at the London Plenary meeting which appeared to generate considerable interest.

The responses provide a useful insight into the level and nature of demand for the proposed **online training course**, which is substantial. A basis for targeting the course should be possible to establish from following-up this information.

Annex I – Template for country action plans

This document is intended to be a guidance template for preparing the country/regional Action plan in Task 1.3.3 and to prompt thinking about the issues involved. It should be read in conjunction with the Description of Work and the timetable specified there and should build on and expand the information provided in the table you completed after the kick off meeting.

These Action Plans are due to be submitted by the end of Month 7 (September) in order to enable completion of a Deliverable in Month 9 (November). They should be finalised following your participation in one of the workshops planned for August/September (at which there will be a session on Action Planning) and will provide a basis for detailed discussion and feedback at the Plenary in November, prior to our completion of D1.4.

The following is the Task description from the DoW

Task 1.3 Action planning

1.3.1 The LoCloud partner in each territory will convene, or otherwise associate with, a planning group involving key players in the cultural sector by Month 4.

1.3.2 Action plans will be prepared by the country partners to identify the steps needed in a territory to implement the IaaS or SaaS solutions for aggregation by Month 7.

D1.4 Consolidated action plans [Month 9]

Checklist of headings/questions for your Action Plan

1 Content and metadata

When do you foresee the metadata for the content listed in the DoW content table being ready for ingestion by the LoCloud aggregator? What steps are needed before then?

Which of the following do you need to do?

- Publish content online
- Clear IPR
- Sign Europeana DEA
- Capture metadata
- Enrich metadata
- Provide unique identifiers/URIs
- Establish a means to export metadata via OAI/SML/CSV/Other
- Map metadata to an intermediary schema: CARARE/LIDO/EAD/other
- Quality assure metadata is ready for Europeana

Which content provider institutions (additional to the ones in the DoW content table) will be approached, with timetable?

2 Politics of aggregation

Which local or regional aggregator service(s) will you need to discuss the work of LoCloud with to agree a mutually beneficial/non-conflicting approach?

Do you foresee any risks or problems in achieving this? If so, please explain.

Which intermediate metadata schemas do you envisage needing to promote and support among content provider institutions and how?

- CARARE
- LIDO
- EAD
- EDM
- ESE
- Other (say which)

3 Infrastructure testing

Which of the lightweight cloud infrastructure components in WP2 do you envisage being involved in testing? Who will be involved?

- Cloud based metadata preparation tools (e.g. MINT)
- Crawler-friendly metadata tagging
- Other methods of ingestion
- Lightweight Digital Library

4 Microservice (SaaS) testing

Which of the microservices in WP3 would you like to be involved with testing. Who will be involved?

- Geolocation enrichment tools
- Metadata Enrichment
- Vocabularies and languages
- Historic place names
- Wikimedia/ crowd sourcing

5 Online training

Who do you see as the main target group for the online training course in WP4? By what means will you introduce and promote the course?

Who do you need to talk to, to ensure maximum interest and support for this?

6 Dissemination

By what means will you gain support from partner organisations and stakeholders in the cultural sector? How will you promote knowledge of the results of LoCloud, coordinate access to local heritage content and advocate the contribution of content/metadata to Europeana' in your region/country?

- Workshops
- Conferences or other events
- Social networks or online forums
- Websites
- Other

How would you promote participation by regions and localities in the planned LoCloud competition (WP6)?

Annex 2 - Action plan and timetable

The content partners' action plans and the timetable for testing activities were reviewed during May 2014. This Annex should be read with Annex 1 of D1.3 which provides the provisional timetable for aggregation and a detailed list of the content.

Content partner objectives: overview

Table 1 (below) sets out the actions which each content providing partner needs to complete for each collection being provided for aggregation to Europeana. The actions are:

- sign the Europeana data exchange agreement
- clear any IPR in the content
- capture metadata for the content
- enrich the available metadata (optional)
- publish the content online
- provide unique identifiers or URIs for the content
- establish a means of exporting the metadata for aggregation

Table 1 highlights in green which actions have been completed by each partner, orange indicates actions which are in progress or have been completed for some collections being provided by a partner, grey shading indicates tasks which are still to be done. More 134 separate collections from more than 170 institutions have been identified by partners so far, naturally individual collections and external content providing institutions are at different stages of preparation at the current time.

One of the main objectives of this content review has been to clarify the status of each collection and the workflow, i.e. which components of the LoCloud infrastructure they will use for aggregation.

The information that has been compiled for each collection is being imported into the LoCloud Event log together with the information presented in Annex 1 of D1.3. This will enable progress with each collection to be monitored as the partners, or their external content providers, complete the actions needed to prepare the content for ingestion.

P n.	Country	Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
1	NRA	NO	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
4	PSNC	PL	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
5	MECD	ES	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
6	KUAS	DK	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
7	BJC	RO	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
8	RCE	NL	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
9	NPU	CZ	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
12	VUKF	LT	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
13	UoY ADS	UK	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
14	IPCHS	SI	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
15	PL	BE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
16	CG33	FR	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
17	Zavad Jara	SI	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
18	Future Library	GR	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
19	FMNF	PT	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
20	UDE	DE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
21	AIT	AT	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
22	ABMR	SE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
23	PSRL	BG	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
24	BGB	RS	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
25	HU	TR	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
26	CUT	CY	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
28	AHAI	IS	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
30	DP	IE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
31	PrifUK KAEG	SK	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
32	FRS	IT	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
33	GKR	HR	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green

Table 1: Content partner progress with content and metadata actions

In table 1 above, green shading highlights completed actions for each collection being made available by the partner. Grey shading indicates work is in progress for one or several of the collections being made available by the partner.

Content partner objectives

P.1 National Archive Norway (NRA)

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadat a captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
National Archives, Norway Local history	to do	completed	to do	to do	to do	Y	Y
Norwegian authority for cultural heritage	to do	completed	to do	to do	to do	to do	Y
Regional archives	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	Y
Local archives	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do
Arkiv i Nordland	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do
Paul Maeyear : Wikimedia collection	to do	completed	in progress	to do	completed		to do

P.4 Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Centre (PSNC)

PSNC is a regional aggregator and will provide metadata in ESE for direct harvesting by the LoCloud aggregator.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metada ta Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Teatr NN	in progress	completed	completed		completed	completed	completed

P.5 Ministerio de Educacion, Cultura y Deporte (MECD)

MECD is a national aggregator and will provide metadata in ESE for direct harvesting by the LoCloud aggregator. In addition some of its external partners will test the Light Weight Digital library and others may provide their metadata for ingestion via the MINT tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Institute for Spanish Cultural Heritage	completed	to do	to do				completed
SG for library coordination	completed	completed	completed	completed	to do	completed	completed
SG for state museums	completed	completed	completed	completed	to do	completed	completed
Museo Arqueológico de Linares. Monográfico de Cástulo	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo Casa de los Tiros	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Artes y Costumbres Populares de Sevilla	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Artes y Costumbres Populares del Alto Guadalquivir	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Cádiz	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Huelva	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Jaén	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Málaga	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Huesca	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Teruel	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Zaragoza	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo del Parque Cultural de Molinos.	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Colección Eleuterio Blasco Ferrer							
Museo Juan Cabré	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo Martín Almagro de Albarracín	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Mallorca	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Albacete	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Ciudad Real	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Cuenca	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Guadalajara	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Santa Cruz	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo Arqueológico Provincial de Ourense	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de las Peregrinaciones y de Santiago	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo Etnológico de Ribadavia	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de los Orígenes	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Museo de Historia	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed
Biblioteca Central de Cantabria	to do	to do	to do	to do	completed	to do	completed
Biblioteca Municipal de Ermua	to do	to do	to do	to do	completed	to do	completed
Fundación Juanelo Turriano	to do	completed	completed	to do	completed	to do	completed
Shadous: memoria fotográfica	to do	to do	to do	to do	completed	to do	completed

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Biblioteca Municipal de Catral	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	completed
Bibliotecas Públicas de Mairena de Aljarafe	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	completed
Biblioteca Miguel Hernández – La Zubia	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	completed
Biblioteca y Archivo Municipal de Monóvar	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	completed
Biblioteca Municipal de Caravaca de la Cruz	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	completed

P.6 Kulturarvsstyrelsen (KUAS)

MECD is a national aggregator for state museums and will provide metadata in LIDO format for direct harvesting by the LoCloud aggregator. In addition it may test ingestion via the MINT tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content publishe d online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
Regin tool for 100 museum collections	to do	in progress	completed	N	completed	completed	in progress

P.7 Biblioteca Județeană „O.Goga” Cluj (BJC)

MECD is a national aggregator and will provide metadata in ESE for direct harvesting by the LoCloud aggregator. .

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
Cluj county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Dolj county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Bihor county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Salaj county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Suceava county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Valcea county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Sibiu county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Hunedoara county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Galati county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Neamt county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Maramures county library		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress
Tribuna Magazine		completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress

Ciucea Memorial Museum		completed	in progress				
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P.8 Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed (RCE)

RCE is a national institution providing its own collections and metadata for ingestion via MINT.

Datasets/collections	European a DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers / URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Historic Cultural Landscapes	to do		in progress	N	Y	Y	OAI-PMH
Archaeological reports	to do		completed		Y	Y	OAI-PMH
Controlled vocab of Dutch archaeology (RNA)	to do		completed	N	Y	Y	OAI-PMH
Regional/local museums	to do						to do
Archaeological depot, province of Gelderland	to do				Y	Y	
VOC.WIC admiraliteit, database WIS database	to do		in progress		Y	Y	XML
Other archaeological depots and museums (not present in DiMCoN)	to do						

P.9 Národní památkový ústav (NPU)

NPU is a national institution providing its own collections and metadata for ingestion via MINT.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers / URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
VAL - significant archaeological sites	completed	completed	completed	N	completed	completed	in progress
SOVAMM	to do	to do	to do	N	to do	to do	to do

P.12 Vilnius University – Faculty of Communication (VUKF)

VUKF is working with local institutions to provide content via the MINT ingestion tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers / URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
Society of Lithuanian Archaeology	in progress	completed	in progress	to do	in progress	to do	in progress
Archaeological thesaurus	completed		completed				
Historic placenames thesaurus	completed		completed				

P.13 University of York, Archaeology Data Service (UoY ADS)

ADS is a national aggregator for the archaeology domain and will provide its content via the MINT ingestion tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers / URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
Grey Literature Library	completed	completed	completed	N	completed	completed	completed
Archived collections	completed	completed	completed	N	completed	completed	completed
PSAS - Proc Soc Ant Scotland	completed	completed	completed	N	completed	completed	completed
Star Carr Archive	completed	completed	completed	N	completed	completed	completed
Wessex Archaeology Archive	completed	completed	completed	N	completed	completed	completed
Southampton Museum's Archive	completed	completed	completed	N	completed	completed	completed

P.14 Javni Zavod Republike Slovenije za Varstvo Kulturne Dediscine (IPCHS)

IPCHS is a national institution and will provide its metadata for harvesting via the MINT service.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers / URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
Archaeological research database	completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	completed	
Works of art database, restoration	completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	in progress	completed	

P.15 Provincie Limburg (PL)

PL is a regional aggregator and will provide metadata for direct harvesting in EDM format. It plans to use the Light Weight Digital Library to provide its own photo archive.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content publishe d online Y/N	Unique identifiers / URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
New collections for Erfgoedplus.b e	completed	completed	in progress	in progress	completed	in progress	completed
Provincie Limburg photo archive	completed	completed					
Placenames	completed	completed	completed		?	?	competed

P.16 Conseil Général de la Gironde (CG33)

CG33 is a regional aggregator and will provide its metadata for direct harvesting in ESE format.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers / URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
Archives of Gironde: FI, iconography collection	completed	completed	completed		completed	completed	completed
Archives of Gironde: 4M Passports	completed	completed	completed		completed	completed	completed
Archives of Gironde: E, Civil registers	completed	completed	completed		completed	completed	completed
Archives of Gironde: other collections	completed	completed	completed		completed	completed	completed
Estuary of Gironde and local historical associations network	to do	completed	completed		in progress	in progress	completed

P.17 Jara. Zavod za razvoj knjižnic (Zavad Jara)

CG33 is a regional aggregator and will provide its metadata for direct harvesting in ESE format.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
KAMRA	completed	completed	completed	to do	in progress	in progress	completed
User generated content	completed	completed	completed	to do	in progress	completed	

P.18 Future Library (Future Library)

Future Library is not a content provider according to the DOW but is in discussions with the libraries listed below about providing content via the Light Weight Digital library.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content publishe d online Y/N	Unique identifiers / URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
Drama							
Kozani							
Trikala							
Levadia							
Korinth							
Naupaktos							
Keratsini- Drapetsona							
Ilioupoli							
Chania							

P.19 Fundação Museu Nacional Ferroviário (FMNF)

FMNF will provide its own collections metadata and those of partner institutions via the MINT ingestion tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Archives collection	completed	completed	completed		in progress	in progress	in progress
Museum collection	completed	completed	completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	
Trains of Portugal	to do	to do	completed	in progress	in progress	in progress	to do

P.20 Universitaet Duisburg-Essen (UDE)

UDE is not a content partner according to the DOW but is in discussion with the insitutions listed, and with the German National Library in Frankfurt, about providing content to Europeana via LoCloud.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs establishe d	Means of exporting metadata in place
Center for International Light art in Unna	to do	to do	to do		to do	to do	to do
Conserve the Sound Essen	to do	to do	to do		to do	to do	to do
Local association Hattingen/Ruhr / Museum in the Iron House	to do	to do	to do		to do	to do	to do
Museum of the city Gladbeck in the Water tower Wittringen	to do	to do	to do		to do	to do	to do
Gustav-Lübcke- Museum Hamm	to do	to do	to do		to do	to do	to do
City Archives of Witten	to do	to do	to do		to do	to do	to do
Kunstmuseum Mülheim an der Ruhr in der Alten Post	to do	to do	to do		to do	to do	to do
The Ruhr- University Bochum - Modern Art Gallery	to do	to do	to do		to do	to do	to do

P.21 Angewandte Informationstechnik Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (AIT)

AIT is a regional aggregator and will provide its metadata for direct harvesting in EDM format.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs establishe	Means of exporting metadata in place
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University of Graz: Archaeological Collections	completed	completed	completed	to do	y	completed	in progress
Hugo Montfort Digital Edition	completed	completed	in progress	to do	y	in progress	in progress
Numismatic Collection at the University of Graz	completed	completed	completed	to do	y	completed	in progress
Visual Art of South-Eastern Europe	completed	completed	completed	to do	y	completed	in progress
Don Juan Archive Vienna: theatre related texts	in progress		in progress	to do	n	in progress	in progress

P.22 Stiftelsen Läns museet Västernorrland (ABMR)

ABMR is a regional aggregator and will provide its metadata for direct harvesting in EDM format.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Ånge kommun (Ånges fotosamling)	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	to do
ABF Kramfors	completed	completed	in progress	to do	to do	to do	
Ulvöarnas kulturarv	completed	completed	in progress	to do	to do	to do	
Birgittamuseet - medicine history	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	to do
Landsarkivet	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	to do
Kubikenborgs skolas intresseförening	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	to do

P23. Pencho Slaveykov Regional Library (PSRL)

AIT is a regional aggregator and will provide its metadata for direct harvesting in ESE format.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content publishe d online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Postcards	completed	completed	completed		completed	to do	completed
Maps	completed	completed	completed		completed	to do	completed
Seals	completed	completed	completed		completed	to do	completed

P24. Biblioteka grada Beograda (BGB)

BGB will provide its content in DC format for ingestion via the MINT tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content publishe d online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Belgrade local history	to do	completed	in progress	in progress	complete d	completed	to do
New content providers	to do						

P.25 Hacettepe Universitesi (HU)

HU is a regional aggregator and will provide its content in DC format for ingestion via the MINT tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadata Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Vehbi Koç & Ankara Research Centre (VEKAN), Ankara collection	in progress	completed	completed	completed	completed	completed	to do

P.26 Cyprus University of Technology (CUT)

CUT is working with the Athena Research Centre to offer local content partners in Cyprus the Omeka digital library. It will provide content for direct harvesting in DCMI terms format.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metada ta Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Archive of Limassol Municipality	in progress	in progress	N/A	Y	in progress	in progress	Y
POSTAL SERVICES	in progress	in progress	N/A	Y	in progress	in progress	Y
Church of Cyprus	in progress	in progress	N/A	Y	in progress	in progress	Y
Church of Cyprus	in progress	in progress	N/A	Y	in progress	in progress	Y
CY Police Forces	in progress	in progress	N/A	y	in progress	in progress	Y
Ministry of Agriculture	in progress	in progress	N/A	Y	in progress	in progress	Y
Press and Information Office CY Government	in progress	in progress	N/A	Y	in progress	in progress	Y
Cyprus Broadcasting Corporation	in progress	in progress	N/A	Y	in progress	in progress	Y

P.28 Minjastofnun Íslands (AHAI)

AHAI is providing its own content for harvesting via the MINT tool, and working with a local museum to provide content via the Light Weight Digital Library.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Archaeological sites	completed	completed	completed	to do	completed	completed	completed
Municipality of Skagafjorour, local museum	in progress	in progress	in progress	to do	to do	in progress	to do

P.30 Discovery Programme (DP)

DP is aggregating content relating to the archaeological heritage on its repository and providing metadata for harvesting via the MINT tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Royal Society of Antiquaries of Ireland Lantern Slide Collection	completed	in progress	in progress	to do	to do	in progress	in progress
Royal Society of Antiquaries of Ireland Du Noyer Collection	completed						
Leo Swan Aerial Collection	completed	completed	in progress	to do	to do	in progress	in progress
Dublin Institute of Advanced Studies 3D Ogham Stone Collection	to do	in progress	in progress	to do	completed	to do	to do
Discovery Programme image collection	completed	completed	in progress	to do	to do	to do	in progress
Carlow Sentinel	to do	Y	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do
Church of Ireland Archives	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
Members of AARG, private collections of archaeological sites	to do	in progress	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do

P.31 Univerzita Komenského Přírodovědecká fakulta Katedra aplikované a environmentální geofyziky (PrifUK KAEG)

PrifUK KAEG is providing its collection and metadata for harvesting via the MINT tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
geophysical images of buried archaeological structures (buildings, chapels..), photos of castels, strongholds, fortifications, historical and cultural buildings	in progress	completed	in progress	Y	to do		to do

P.32 Fondazione Ranieri di Sorbello (FRS)

FRS is providing its metadata for harvesting via the MINT tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metadat a Y/N	Content publishe d online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
SAMIRA	completed	in progress	completed		in progress	in progress	in progress

P.33 Gradska knjiznica Rijeka (GKR)

GKR is a regional aggregator and is providing its metadata for harvesting in DCMI format via the MINT tool.

Datasets/ collections	Europeana DEA signed Y/N	IPR cleared	Metadata captured	Enrich metada ta Y/N	Content published online Y/N	Unique identifiers/ URIs established	Means of exporting metadata in place
Local history collections, newspapers and magazines	to do	in progress	in progress	Y	Y	N	oai-pmh
Postcards	to do	in progress	in progress	Y	in progress	N	oai-pmh
Local museum items	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do	N	oai-pmh

Microservices: timetable for testing

Microservice	Mar	April	May	02-Jun	09-Jun	16-Jun	28-Jul	04-Aug	05-Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov
Vocabulary												
Metadata enrichment												
Historic placenames												
Geocoding												
Wikimedia service												

The following partners will participate in the testing of microservices:

- Vocabularies microservice lead by AIT, test partners include: Provincie Limburg, Future Library, RCE, ABMR and NRA
- Metadata enrichment lead by EHU, test partners include: Provincie Limburg, PSRL, CUT, Future Library, AHAI, FRS, RCE, NRA, Zavod Jara, ABMR, HU, UoY ADS, AIT
- Historic place names lead by VUFK, test partners include: Provincie Limburg, CUT, Future Library, FRS, VUKF, RCE, NRA, BGB, PrifUK KAEG, ABMR, HU, AIT
- Geocoding lead by AVINET and IPCHS, test partners to be confirmed
- Wikimedia lead by ARC, test partners include: NRA (Paul Maerhaert), ADS, others

Infrastructure : timetable for testing

Components	20-Jun	30-Jun	15-Jul	30-Jul	15-Aug	30-Aug	15-Sep
Harvester - OAI-PMH							
Harvester - MINT							
Harvester - LDL							
Ingest							
Validation (CARARE,ESE,EDM,LIDO)							
Transformation (CARARE,ESE)							
Transformation (LIDO)							
Enrichment							
Publishing							
Workflow - Notifications							
Single Sign-On							
Event Log Integration							
Statistics							